

Sabria Schouten

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Concrete Terror: Personified Monstrous Forces in Ann Petry's *The Street*

Introduction

In literature, there are a number of elements that can make a text Gothic. Dark and gloomy castles, insanity, the sublime and the supernatural are all indicative of a literary work's belonging to the Gothic genre (Smith 4). The motif of the monster is yet another such element, particularly characteristic of earlier Gothic texts (Smith 7). However, not all Gothic literature features a physically monstrous and therefore terrifying creature like the one brought forth in Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein* (1818). This does not necessarily mean that the monster stops existing, but rather it may have taken on a different form for, as Andrew Smith explains, "the Gothic (...) mutates across historical, national, and generic boundaries as it reworks images drawn from different ages and places" (4). Thus, Gothic motifs and tropes must be read and understood in their historical context as that which is terrifying is redefined over time and in accordance with contemporary conventions (Smith 7). One literary work in which the monster and terror take on a novel and distinct form, contrasting with the 'traditional' monster, is Ann Petry's *The Street* (1946).

Set in the 1940s, the plot gravitates around Lutie Johnson, a black woman who seeks the safety and security of a home for herself and her son. On this quest she is faced with obstacles that reflect the system of oppression against black women operating in 20th-century New York. Living in Harlem, more precisely on 116th Street, Lutie comes to fear the street and some of its inhabitants. Yet how can something made out of concrete instil terror? This paper seeks to argue that a personification of the monstrous can be identified in the novel, while not being contained or limited to a physical, concrete form and thus also operating as a monstrous force (Radomska 226). At the same time, the street in all its power can be interpreted to breed its own monsters, as it influences characters such as Mrs Hedges and William Jones, and it ultimately impacts Lutie herself, leading her to act monstrously, murdering Boots Smith and abandoning her son (Shockley 443). In order to understand the monstrous in *The Street*, elements of race, gender, sexuality and class are analysed throughout the essay, as they seem to be directly responsible for the influence of

monstrous forces and for the terror that Lutie is faced with while living on 116th Street. The paper further suggests that a Gothic reading of *The Street* can lead the reader to reconsider whether something must be bound to a physical form in order to be terrifying.

Contextualizing the Monstrous

A Gothic reading of *The Street*, in contrast with a realist one which vividly portrays the hardships that the lives of black women in the United States are riddled with, allows for the discernment of the monstrous as a driving-force of these hardships (Shockley 456). While there might not be an outwardly monstrous figure terrifying Lutie, the title of the novel is suggestive of what it is that brings fear into her life, namely the street itself.

The novel traces Lutie Johnson's endeavour to attain a secure home for herself and for her son, Bub. Having worked for a middle class white family, Lutie adopted their fervent belief in the American dream which allows anyone, as long as hard work is involved, to transgress their circumstances and attain a better life. However, her identity as a black, working class woman separated from her husband makes this goal impossible to reach and the only home she can afford is a shabby Harlem apartment on 116th Street where she is faced with the presence of William Jones, the apartment building's superintendent, whom Lutie instinctively fears, and Mrs Hedges, a snake-eyed woman whose piercing glance from her first-floor window unsettles passers-by. The protagonist is determined to leave the street and its uncanny inhabitants and she sets out to make enough money to move into a secure home, knowing that money is "the only thing that could get her and Bub out of that street. And the lack of it would keep them there forever." (Petry 153).

Lutie seeks to acquire the money she needs on her own terms, and this proves to be challenging. Petry portrays Lutie as an attractive young woman, which consequently leads all the male characters in the novel to express their desire for her. Jones, the musician Boots Smith and Junto, the white man whose decisions directly impact Lutie, all pose a threat to her values and her ownership over her own body (Shockley 439). What is more, Mrs Hedges suggests that if Lutie wishes to make more money, she knows a "nice white gentleman" (Petry 77) who is interested in her and would be willing to pay significantly for her companionship. Lutie is thus placed in an impossible position where the people she is surrounded by seem to imply that she has no ownership over her own sexuality and that as a black woman she is available to desirous black and white men (Shockley 439). The ways in which other characters act upon Lutie contribute to her feeling of

being trapped, of being unable to transcend her circumstances and leave 116th Street, which she comes to perceive as a personification of everything that hinders her from attaining the security of domesticity far from Harlem. It becomes representative of the power of white men over the fate of black women, as Junto decides what she can and cannot attain, an idea that shall be discussed further in the following sections.

Scholar Evie Shockley's approach towards analysing the context within which the monstrous operates in *The Street* is one that identifies in Lutie Johnson the author's Gothic double (440). A Gothic reading of the novel allows for an understanding of the systemic racism at play in 20th-century New York, a force that Ann Petry herself was familiar with, as she, too, lived in Harlem for some time (Shockley 440). Shockley states that Lutie represents a double that has been endowed with the same middle class values that Petry herself had been brought up with, while also being suggestive of "Petry's ultimate, untapped potential for behaving monstrously" (442). This potential, Shockley explains, is the result of living in Harlem, which has implications for the character of anyone residing on its streets (442). This inextricable link between the environment one lives in and character is something that Lutie herself reflects on, thinking that "no one could live on a street like this and stay decent" (Petry 211).

Identifying the Monstrous

According to scholar Daniela Carpi, monsters are "terrifying creatures that represent complete alterity and challenge every basic notion of self and identity within a cultural paradigm" (1). Such a definition, as it includes the notion of a creature, presupposes the physical nature of the monster. Something is monstrous, Carpi further explains, when it acts against norms and values, against cultural conventions (1). Arguably, for Lutie Johnson, the monstrous is all that which operates outside of her middle class values. It is also represented by the forces that would rob her of her ownership and of the potential of leaving the street to find a safe and secure home. These forces culminate in the street and Petry's description thereof invites an interpretation of the street as a living entity, at times shapeless, at times tangible, with its own agency that it exerts upon all its inhabitants, one way or another leading to their dehumanization. This is made evident in the following excerpt:

“In that very apartment house in which she was now living, the same combination of circumstances had evidently made the Mrs Hedges who sat in the street-floor window turn to running a fairly-kept whorehouse - but unmistakably a whorehouse; and the superintendent of the building - well, the street had pushed him into basements away from light and air until he was being eaten up by some horrible obsession” (Petry 52).

The circumstances referred to are the influence of places like 116th Street and being black, both of which directly impact the lives of Harlem’s residents who, as the novel indicates, are forced into drab apartment buildings on streets that turn people into monsters, into something less than human, because they are black. Lutie vows that something like this will not happen to her, and she determined to keep fighting against the influences of the street that she has been pushed into because of her race (Petry 52). The above-quoted passage indicates that the street has volition, it holds power over its residents, forces changes in their circumstances and subsequently, as Shockley explains, in their characters (442).

Mrs Hedges, for instance, after moving on 116th Street as a consequence of her friendship with Junto, commences the operation of a brothel in her apartment. Lutie perceives her as an ominous presence, always glancing up and down the street, aware of all the goings on, with the “appearance of a creature that had strayed from some other planet” (Petry 218). While the character’s uncanniness is highlighted in this quote, Lutie is aware that the street had turned her into such a creature (Petry 52). Arguably, Mrs Hedges can appear monstrous because she seeks to deter the protagonist from her middle class values and from her agency and ownership of her own body and sexuality (Shockley 439). She does this by suggesting that she knows a white man who can offer Lutie money in return for her companionship. The identity of this white man is revealed later in the narrative, as the reader discovers that Mrs Hedges was referring to Junto. Through Lutie’s perspective marked by the quote: “if you live on this damn street you’re supposed to want to earn a little money sleeping around nights. With nice white gentlemen” (Petry 77), her frustration at the assumption that other characters in the novel have about her is made evident, namely that because she is a single black woman living in Harlem she is more than willing to be sexual with black and white men alike, especially if remuneration is involved (Shockley 439).

When it comes to Jones, the Super, Lutie’s first encounter with this character reveals her fear for him. She meets him when he shows her the apartment she will rent on 116th Street, and in

this process the protagonist carries out an inner conflict in which she is aware of his desire for her, while dismissing her fears as foolish and inaccurate. The descriptions used to portray Jones, however, are closely linked to the monstrous, for when walking down the stairs from the apartment “she half-expected to see horns sprouting from behind his ears” and “she wouldn’t have been greatly surprised if, in place of one of the heavy work shoes on his feet, there had been a cloven hoof that twitched and jumped” (Petry 19). Lutie even comes to perceive him as less than human, thinking instead that “he had been chained to buildings until he was like an animal” (Petry 175). What is also associated with this character is the idea of being “cellar-crazy” (Petry 220), which ties into the Gothic notion of insanity and indicates that the street influences its inhabitants’ characters by acting upon their sanity.

Mrs Hedges and the Super have been interpreted by Shockley to represent the monstrous and the vampire or devil (451). She associates them with the Gothic undead, stating that they have been symbolically buried on 116th Street, trapped there for so long that they have turned into monstrous creatures (451). Consequently, Mrs Hedges and Jones seem to act as intermediaries between Lutie and the street, having been directly impacted by it and in turn making efforts to establish Lutie’s belonging to this concrete, dehumanizing prison. This can be discerned for example from Mrs Hedges’ offer to Lutie to make extra money and in the scene where Jones tries to drag her into the basement. Both these instances can be read as endeavours to pull Lutie into their world, actively contributing to her transformation into a similar creature. Thus, by interacting with these characters Lutie is presented with her own potential monstrous nature, the manifestation of which would cement her belonging to the street as she could become “a member of this ghastly gothic family” (Shockley 451). But how do concrete sidewalks and cramped apartment buildings have the power to turn human beings into monsters?

The Monstrous in the Concrete

In her article, Shockley briefly alludes to an interpretation of the street as the monster in Petry’s novel, referring to it as “actively vampiric” (Shockley 452). This idea is presented as Lutie reflects on how the street “sucked the humanity out of people - slowly, surely, inevitably” (Petry 211). The dehumanizing effect of living on 116th Street is thus made evident, as the vampiric street creates its own monsters by eventually yet inevitably sinking its fangs into its residents, which, as Shockley indicates, has repercussions for their character and leads them to behave monstrously (442).

While Shockley does not explicitly mention this, it is important to add that the street is ascribed agency in the novel. Lutie becomes increasingly aware of the power and agency that 116th Street is endowed with and she is eager to leave before it can take hold of her or Bub. The language and imagery employed by Petry give the impression that the concrete itself is capable of acting, and more importantly of acting upon people, an idea that Lutie's reflections reveal. While she had decided to fight against the street, not fearing it initially, her worries turn towards her son, "because this street and the other streets just like it would, if he stayed in them long enough, do something terrible to him" (Petry 178). At the same time, she comes to believe the streets of Harlem "would do something equally terrible to her" (Petry 178). Such fragments confer life upon the street and almost grant it the status of a character, the most monstrous one of all, as it can 'do things' to those residing on it. The passages indicate that Lutie senses that no matter how hard she fights against it, the street will eventually take its toll on her, as it has on Mrs Hedges and Jones, but they also highlight her awareness of 'the monstrous in the concrete'.

The monstrous shown forth in *The Street* contrasts greatly with the traditional Gothic motif of the monster as an outwardly terrifying and convention-breaking creature (Carpi 1). Scholar Marietta Radomska has investigated novel manifestations of the monstrous and her findings are significant for an understanding of how the monstrous operates in Petry's novel. Radomska explains that numerous narratives define the monster "by pointing at the excess, deficiency or displacement of organic matter" (216), establishing the physicality of the monstrous whose appearance is in itself terrifying. She, however, reconsiders the nature of the monstrous as tied to a physical form, arguing for a new ontology of life that involves an understanding of the uncontainable, arguing that the monstrous transgresses and is not limited to matter, be it organic or inorganic (217). Drawing on the phenomenon of 'deterritorialisation' which signifies the "forces and intensities that take life beyond itself, beyond the containment of established boundaries and relations", she indicates that the uncontainable is characterized by excess, a typical trait of the monstrous (226). Thus, the monstrous need not be allocated an outwardly horrific body in order to be terrifying, as the non-living and inorganic can also be endowed with the monstrous, while it also operates outside of any material boundaries in the shape of "forces and intensities" (Radomska 226).

Such an analysis sheds new light on *The Street* and the monstrous therein, as it allows for an understanding of the modern monstrous, of what is terrifying in the 20th century, not as

something with a body, but as something that acts directly and invisibly on people, particularly on people of color. Lutie's perception of the street as having volition and ascribing it agency indicates that the monstrous is present on 116th Street, despite it being non-living, as Radomska has indicated (226). At the same time, it also operates at a level outside of the inorganic, which does not represent the monstrous itself, but is rather a personification thereof, the street being something that the monstrous seeps into, but it is not confined to. This is indicated by Lutie's reflection that all streets in Harlem are to be feared, not just 116th Street and that there is no escaping the terrifying force as long as one is black and can only pay so much rent (Petry 73).

The question remains of what endows 116th Street with such life-force so as to become personified, conferring it power to act upon Lutie and her son? Arguably what bestows these qualities upon it is the systemic racism deeply rooted in American society, which has become permeated in the very concrete of 116th Street. This idea is suggested in the quote: "streets like the one she lived on were no accident. They were the North's lynch mobs, she thought bitterly; the method the big cities used to keep Negroes in their place" (Petry 297). Race is what pushed people like Mrs Hedges, Jones and Lutie into Harlem, and the protagonist thinks of how "from the time she was born, she had been hemmed into an ever-narrowing space, until now she was very nearly walled in and the wall had been built up brick by brick by eager white hands" (Petry 297).

On 116th Street, the most prominent hands building this wall are those of Junto. He is Lutie's personal oppressor, as he is the one who decides that she is not to be paid for her singing, robbing her of the possibility of leaving the street. Junto's presence seeps into the walls of Lutie's apartment and follows her as she walks down the street. He is initially perceived as a piercing silence, but as his presence grows more and more prominent, as the silence grows more and more unbearable, she realizes that "the creeping, silent thing that she had sensed in the theater, in the beauty parlor, was here in her living room (...) Before it had been formless, shapeless, a fluid moving mass - something disembodied that she couldn't see, could only sense. Now, as she stared at the couch, the thing took on form, substance. She could see what it was. It was Junto" (Petry 386). Thus, once Lutie discovers Junto's direct impact on her life, she identifies him as the animating force of the street, as his presence and by extension that of systemic racism are what instil terror, for this is what drives people into Harlem and into the jaws of a concrete beast that changes their characters and dehumanizes them.

The shapeless power, the invisible yet potent force that, alongside monstrous characters such as Jones and Mrs Hedges, directly acts upon Lutie whose race, gender and class make her susceptible to this monstrous force as the novel progresses is representative of the historical context of 20th-century New York, in which racism is firmly established as a social norm. The “eager white hands” (Petry 297) that Lutie identifies as the culprit for her ‘entombment’, as Shockley would suggest (451), indicate that the power of the street is the power to trap black people. In Lutie’s case, she is trapped by an invisible power that becomes concrete both in the form of the street and of Junto, as both exert their agency and prolong her stay on 116th Street.

Conclusion

Lutie’s initial determination to fearlessly fight against the street slowly dissipates throughout the novel, culminating in the ending where, after Jones and Mrs Hedges have made their impact, after Junto as a symbol of inescapable systemic racism has been identified and after what she feared most, namely that the street would ‘do something’ to Bub is materialized, Lutie is driven to act monstrously, murdering Boots Smith. While she kills him she harbours the illusion of beating the street, yet she can never hope to kill 116th Street and all it symbolizes, namely American racism in the 20th century. The street and the concrete terror it comprises had sucked the humanity out of her like a vampire and led her to act monstrously, committing a murder and abandoning Bub (Shockley 452). Even though Lutie leaves New York, 116th Street and all other similar streets will continue to exist in all their power after she has left, continuing to use their agency, to exercise their force and breed monsters. What is more, her identity as a black woman will probably drive her into an equally monstrous street in another city, for racism is not limited to New York, but is rather a monstrous force present and personified in the concrete of numerous American streets. Thus, Lutie’s circumstances seem to relate to Radomska’s statement that “we cannot escape the monstrous (...) instead, we may and should learn anew how to relate to it” (227). The monstrous will continue to exist, albeit in a different context, and Lutie will be forced to navigate monstrous forms of oppression in a new city.

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